

SYNTHESIS AND APPLICATION OF ALIGNED,

DISCONTINUOUS COMPOSITES

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Studies of fibre alignment by convergent flow led to the development of two processes (1) by which aligned sheets, mats and shells could be generated from discontinuous fibres and used efficiently as reinforcements. Both processes involved deposition and recovery of aligned fibres from a liquid suspension on a draining surface, the first by vacuum filtration, the second by centrifugal action. For a given rate of deposition, the centrifugal process has proved more effective in preparing highly-aligned uniform sheets and cylinders of felt which pack well during moulding. The main industrial interest at the present time is in using these felts, made up as a prepreg of carbon fibres, to form complex components with relative ease. Fig 1 shows an example of the type of material.

This paper deals with two recent developments, the use of the numerical flow properties of these prepreg felts to guide the shaping operations in component manufacture, and the high mechanical properties which are now attained both in simple composites and in hybrids of intimately-mixed short fibres. In these hybrids, the reinforcing strength of HMS graphite fibre changes markedly with hybrid composition, and a general theory is presented which explains these observations and can be used for assessing other hybrid systems.

Fig 1 - Draped single ply of HTS carbon prepreg

1 Tensile Strength of Unidirectional Laminates,
Continuous versus Discontinuous

Early work with the filtration process materials showed a marked discrepancy between the strength of discontinuous fibre composites and those of continuous fibre (1). Even when strengths were corrected to the same fibre content, the discontinuous materials proved much weaker. Although this was not likely to influence their use purely for stiffening structures of complex shape, it was seen by the aerospace industries as a long-term constraint. As fibre alignment was improved, however, the observed tensile strength rose, incidentally proving that strength predictions based on regular (brickwork) theoretical models were incorrect. It was finally decided to make a definitive, independent comparison of tensile strength of press-moulded laminates of HTS Grafil fibre (type 130SC) to measure what discrepancies there were between centrifugal plant material and continuous fibre.

The fibre and resin (Epoxy DX210) were bought to specification and a single batch was divided for preparation of continuous and discontinuous prepreg sheets by a specialist firm and by PERME using the centrifugal process, respectively. Test panels were produced by compression moulding and many checks of consistency and quality were first carried out by various participating laboratories, the details of which are given elsewhere (2).

The conclusive testing of tensile strength and stiffness was conducted at the laboratories of AQD Harefield. This ran to 36 test panels of eight specimens each (9 panels of each prepreg at 50% and at 55% nominal volume loadings). The differences in recorded properties then proved so small that there was some difficulty in assigning their origins. The results for each panel were corrected for fibre volume loading to a notional 50% by volume, and the observed mean tensile strength could be expressed as a proportion of the stiffness to discount any factors which affected both properties equally.

Table 1

	Axial Youngs Modulus GPa	Axial UTS as % of Modulus
50% Nominal Group		
Discontinuous	109 ± 4.34	1.055 ± 0.039
Continuous	116 ± 2.87	1.07 ± 0.029
55% Nominal Group		
Discontinuous	109 ± 2.99	1.02 ± 0.030
Continuous	116 ± 4.87	1.12 ± 0.025

The conclusions were as follows:

- a The relative stiffness of discontinuous fibre composite was known precisely and was 6% lower than that of continuous laminates.
- b This elastic difference was also the main distinction observed in the strength. Inspection of individual means for the discontinuous panels revealed a falling trend of fibre reinforcing strength from 1.07 of modulus to 1.03 of modulus as volume loading rose from 50 to 55%.
- c The apparent increase in reinforcing strength of the continuous fibre with increased volume loading remains unexplained, and was not reproduced in

Fig 2 - Effect of moulding pressure on maximum volume loading of HTS carbon fibre

Fig 3 - Maximum load and elongation versus ply angle for single plies

batches tested elsewhere. In these circumstances the mean, 1.09% of modulus, appears to be the correct baseline.

d Therefore at 50% volume loading, discontinuous fibre composite is most likely to be 8% weaker in tension than continuous, while at 55% by volume, this difference widens to about 12%. These results are in accordance with simple predictions (1) for the fibre length used, 3 mm, compared with an estimated critical length of 0.2 mm.

2 The Flow Properties of Aligned Prepreg Felts

With the inherent differences of unidirectional strength between continuous and discontinuous reinforcements shown to be small, attention was turned to exploring the scope of the material in fabrication processes. The consolidation curves of HTS fibre from the centrifugal process and filtration process are shown in Fig 2, from which it is clear that compression moulding and expansion moulding would be feasible for both materials, but that for autoclave moulding the centrifugal process has more to offer.

Spot checks on the stretching properties of the two forms of prepreg felt showed that their behaviour is very similar. The detailed work reported here required substantial supplies of felt and so material available from the filtration process was used, accepting a corresponding reduction in fibre content and in strength of the composites.

When a cloth is draped over a curved surface, it fits the surface by adjusting the angle between the warp and weft of which it is composed, so that final orientations are determined by the curvature and not by the stress system. Although similar characteristics can indeed be obtained by distorting prepregs which have been plied together, a discontinuous prepreg may also be deformed in longitudinal and transverse directions with less disturbance of the orientation. The value of such leathery material in preparing shaped components is therefore related to the amount of deformation which can be used and to the extent to which orientation can be controlled. The question of the loads required to bring about deformation is less important, although clearly for hand assembly a fairly soft material is needed. However, for more precise work, forming jigs will be needed and the capability of softening a harder material only locally by warming it is also attractive. This leads to shaping processes analogous to the spinning of metals or to the working of clay. In all cases, it is important to know the relative loads required to initiate the different types of permanent deformation. Where prepreg materials are used, the resins are sufficiently viscous to prevent any gross elastic recovery of either cloth or felt.

2.1 Macroscopic Strain in Single Plies

A first set of experiments was carried out by cutting strips of felt prepreg 30 mm wide, marking them with grid lines and stretching a gauge length of 100 mm in a tensile testing machine at uniform rate of extension. The loads required naturally varied over several orders of magnitude with the rate of extension chosen and with the type and age of the epoxy in the prepreg, but extension behaviour itself was quite consistent. The deformation load rose to a peak, then dropped away slowly. Since deformation on a falling load curve invites local thinning or tearing of the material, the elongation at maximum load was recorded, see Fig 3. The permissible extension identified in this way rises from 5% axially to some 50% in the transverse direction, while the maximum load follows the pattern of a maximum resolved stress theory of composite strength. It is interesting that the axial value of 5% is rather small for the instability point of

Fig 4 - Post maximum load deformation modes

Fig 5 - Stretch-formed CFRP shell and flange

randomly overlapping fibres, but is perhaps too large to be related to a characteristic shear strain of the porous matrix, which is magnified by two orders of magnitude due to the aspect ratio of the fibres. This is also clearly illustrated by the difference of axial and transverse peak loads.

Final rupture of the strips (Fig 4) shows various mechanisms at work. For small angles off-axis (up to 5° in this case) transverse tearing occurs after appreciable reduction in width, accompanied by local internal splitting when the alignment of fibres is enhanced by the elongation. Shearing off between parallel fibres occurs only between 5 and 15° off-axis, beyond which fibres rotate away from the load direction, unlike similar crossed plies, which jointly rotate to align themselves with the load. Stretching of the porous sheet transverse to the fibres produces slight rotation toward the stretch direction as they behave like a pin-jointed framework, or the opening of a collapsed lazy-tongs.

2.2 Effects of Constraint - Multiple Plies

We have found in practice that the prepreg may safely be stretched more than 5% (the point of maximum load) in the axial direction by supporting or constraining it against a surface to ensure that the strain is distributed evenly, and also by "coaxing" the material, ie repeated loading and relaxation. Conditions of constraint also arise when plies are laminated together by warm pressing, eg an initial orientation of $\pm 20^\circ$ was stretched 12% in the 0 direction under rising load, but with a 50% reduction in width as the fibres rotated toward the test axis. In the pseudo-isotropic array ($0 \pm 60^\circ$) elongation to peak load was increased to 7% along the 0 direction, but this value was then common to other directions since rotational movement was inhibited by the third set of fibres.

2.3 Effect of Stretching on the Tensile Strength of Laminates

The tensile strength of stretched material was measured on parallel-sided strip test pieces cut from cured laminates (914 epoxy matrix) which had previously been stretched as a single block 230 x 152 x 2 mm. The strength was measured in the stretch direction in all cases. Failures were distributed fairly evenly down the specimen length. A separate exercise had shown that this method was satisfactory since the measured tensile strength of unstretched material (Condition A) was greater than that predicted by Weibull statistics from the observed flexural strength and variability. For the wider sections of prepreg stretched for these tests, the stable elongations at peak load (Condition B) were slightly reduced. The elongations and mechanical properties were also measured after a fall of 40% from the peak load (Condition C). The plying arrangements and the respective elongations are given in Table 2.

Six specimens of each orientation and condition were tested. Although this number cannot provide an accurate estimate of variability, the mean values and significant changes in the mean can be identified. The changes in strength obtained are shown in Table 2.

The following observations were made

1 0° off-axis - both the fall in UTS and the increase in variability, as the elongation in the prepreg is increased, are significant at the 5% level. Close inspection of the felts during elongation had shown that small "slips" or separation of fibre ends had occurred in regions about 1 mm across. These were stable in the stretching prepreg but could well account for local weakening of the moulded unidirectional composite.

Table 2. Results of Tests on Stretched Prepreg (Filtration Process)

Sample	UTS MN m ⁻²	Observed Standard Deviation MN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation %	Weight % CF in Prepreg	Vol % CF in Composite
0° off axis					
1 No deformation	665.8	46.7	7.0	40.6	39.2
2 3.5% stretch	599.2	110.2	18.4	44.8	41.9
3 6% stretch	457.0	92.6	20.3	42.1	40.0
+60° 0°					
1 No deformation	273.8	21.5	7.8	42.9	40.22
2 5% stretch	266.1	17.2	6.5	43.1	41.9
3 18.7% stretch	327.7	23.1	7.1	41.4	41.5
+30° 90°					
1 No deformation	204.6	12.1	5.9	41.1	38.7
2 5% stretch	230.0	25.2	10.9	41.5	40.8
3 16.7% stretch	236.5	37.3	15.8	40.8	37.2
+40° off axis					
1 No deformation	246.5	13.6	5.5	41.4	39.7
2 25% stretch	343.9	52.8	15.4	42.1	45.9
40° off axis					
1 No deformation	78.6	12.3	15.7	41.8	38.9
2 15% stretch	60.3	10.5	17.4	42.2	43.2

6 tensile coupons per composite

Voidage < 1% in all cases.

The values for UTS have not been normalised with respect to fibre volume fraction.

2 0° + 60° - the interesting point here is that the composite made from over-stretched prepreg is significantly stronger than the other two composites. Whilst a change of ply angle from 60 to 53° is detectable this is not sufficient to account for a 20% increase in UTS. It may be that the +60° crossplies were able to constrain the 0° layer so that the fibre orientation improved without developing weak areas. This argument is supported by the improved packing in the composite (ie the ratio vol % CF in the cured laminate/wt % CF in the prepreg increased).

3 +30° 90° - the composite strengths appear to increase with prepreg elongation. However, there is a large and significant rise in variability which masks this so that the differences in strength do not appear to be significant. There is also a change in ply angle from +30° in the unstretched state to +25° in the stretched state.

4 +40° - the strength of the composite made from stretched prepreg is approximately 40% greater than that made from unstretched prepreg - due to the fibre rotation. This fibre rotation is not uniform across the board (due to grip constraints) being about 5° at the outside edge of the board up to about 18° at the centre of the board - which gives rise to the high variability.

2.4 Application to Forming Processes

The data for the stretching of single plies show how orthodox patchwork assembly methods can be used to contour complex shapes, particularly double curvatures, while retaining control of fibre orientation. The work with multiple plies also suggests an alternative approach, by producing a simple generic shape first, then drawing it to the final shape and to those orientations which are acceptable. The demonstration gearbox shell and heavy flange shown in Fig 5 was made in this way from a simple conical skin, which was then autoclave-moulded. The shell resisted both bending and torsion and carried load smoothly into the rigid flange. The estimated weight saving over metallic construction was approximately 25% and is capable of further refinement.

In general, we have found that this type of prepreg has a complementary role to that of woven cloth or wound filaments, and can often be used in conjunction with them. It can be laid up in any planar arrangement and its ability to distort in at least three different modes is a real advantage. Woven fabrics can be rotated in tension from $\pm 45^\circ$ to perhaps $\pm 20^\circ$ extending a maximum of some 30% as they do so. However, the combined transverse flow and rotational modes allow the discontinuous material to cover the full range from $\pm 90^\circ$ to $\pm 10^\circ$, beyond which axial stretching becomes significant. In this case, if the axially stretched layer is to be highly-stressed, it must be carefully supported during flow.

3 Intimately-mixed, Aligned Hybrids

The centrifugal alignment process offers the opportunity to investigate many short-fibre hybrid systems with a view to optimising properties and cost, i.e. providing a family of materials for different purposes. To provide carbon prepreg materials of increased specific stiffness, we have first made practical measurements and theoretical estimates of the HTS-HMS system.

Table 3. Strength and Stiffness of Unidirectional HTS-HMS Carbon-Epoxy Hybrids in GPa, 50% Fibre by Volume, Coefficients of Variation in Brackets

Composition	Flexural Modulus	Tensile Modulus	Tensile Strength	As % of Flexural Modulus	ILSS (MPa)
HMS	159 (7)	151 (15)	0.609 (11)	0.38	67.8 (7)
0.75 HMS 0.25 EHTS	138 (4)	129 (11)	0.604 (10)	0.44	68.4 (9)
0.5 HMS 0.5 EHTS	136 (7)	-	0.907 (10)	0.67	81.4 (7)
0.25 HMS 0.75 EHTS	118 (4)	105 (6)	0.936 (11)	0.79	79.4 (13)
0.25 HMS 0.75 HTS	113 (5)	108 (12)	0.996 (9)	0.88	95.3 (5)
EHTS*	99 (3)	97 (11)	1.156 (9)	1.16	88.7 (14)
HTS	100 (3)	114 -	1.14 -	1.14	

*Revised (lower) surface treatment of HTS

Fig 6 - Work of fracture of experimental HMS graphite hybrids

Fig 7 - Proposed transitions in reinforcing strength of a brittle fibre with composition

The compositions chosen are given in Table 3. Ten parallel strip specimens were tested for each composition. Extension to fracture was monitored with an Instron extensometer and only in one specimen (of 0.25 HMS, 0.75 HTS) was any non-linear behaviour detected prior to failure. Inspection of the results show immediately that the strength contribution of the HMS fibre is greater than expected where it comprises half or less of the reinforcement. When strength is expressed as a fraction of the modulus it is clear that the HMS fibre has in fact attained a stress twice that which it normally exhibits. There are no significant trends in interlaminar shear strength, but some tendency for the work of fracture of the systems studied to be better than average when the HMS is in the minority (Fig 6).

Taking into account the work of Aveston and Sillwood (3) at small volume additions of HMS, we suggest that the HMS fibre in fact assumes three characteristic values in a hybrid, ie its brittle strength, the bundle strength that it should ideally attain, and when it is heavily supported by other fibres, its average strength (Fig 7). Now Hitchon and Phillips (4) for example show that the strength and variability of HMS fibre at 0.5 mm gauge length is virtually equal to that of HTS fibre of the same length. Thus if HTS fibre attains 1.2% of its modulus as a reinforcing strength, then HMS should attain 0.8%. If their data from many tests is averaged up, this is what it does predict (Table 4). That is, at 0.5 mm gauge length there appears to be little variation of strength with length and it is perhaps legitimate to treat the bundle strength according to Coleman as an approximation to the reinforcing strength (Fig 8).

3.1 Fibres, Layers and Bundles of Low Variability

If both sets of fibres in a hybrid behave elastically, and each has a very consistent value of strength then only when they both have the same strain to break does the tensile strength of the hybrid obey the rule of mixtures law. If the strains differ, then the strength must go through a trough. This is shown in Fig 9, where strength is plotted against composition from all A to all B. Lines of constant strain such as RP and the composite modulus EE can be drawn from O. Then if B has the lower strain to break, PR represents the strength contribution of B, SB that of A. To the left of T, the A phase eventually carries all the load, assuming it is unaffected by the breakage of B, ie compositions along TS will show a yield point or knee in their stress-strain curves. Those to the right of T will be elastic. For fibres or layers of very consistent strength then, PTS describes the strength of A-B hybrids.

By setting down the equations representing PR and SB, the composition of the minimum at T can be expressed as the relative proportion of A

$$a_T = [1 + R_E (R_S - 1)]^{-1} \text{ with } R_E = \frac{E_A}{E_B}$$

the ratio of the moduli, $R_S = \frac{\Sigma A}{\Sigma B}$ the ratio of the elastic breaking strains.

Similarly the maximum depression of strength (at T) relative to the rule of mixtures value is given by

$$\frac{S_M}{S_C} = 1 + \frac{R_S - 1}{R_S}$$

and is therefore never less than half this value. However, it is clear from

Table 4. Strength of 50 mm, 5 mm and 0.5 mm Long Carbon Fibres

Observed (AERE)					Assumed for this work				
Fibre type and length	Mean Strength MN/m ² x 10 ⁻²	Number of Tests	Standard Deviation MN/m ² x 10 ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation per cent	CV Assumed	Bundle Strength as Fraction of Average (from Fig 8)	Average		Bundle Strength (% E)
							GPa	% E	
<u>A 50 mm</u>									
<u>Type 1 (15BR)</u>									
1st Series	27.1	121	5.66	20.9	20	0.68	2.6	0.68	0.46
2nd Series	24.7	24	4.29	17.4					
<u>Type 2 (11R)</u>									
1st Series	30.7	125	4.57	14.9	15	0.73	3.0	1.24	0.91
2nd Series	27.5	25	3.68	13.4					
<u>B 5 mm</u>									
<u>Type 1 (15BR)</u>									
1st Series	41.2	10	7.41	18.0	20	0.68	3.5	0.92	0.62
2nd Series	29.4	10	7.07	24.0					
<u>Type 2 (11R)</u>									
1st Series	37.1	10	6.87	18.5	15	0.73	3.65	1.51	1.10
2nd Series	36.3	10	5.24	14.4					
<u>C 0.5 mm</u>									
<u>Type 1 (15BR)</u>									
1st Series	43.6	10	7.10	16.3	16	0.72	4.1	1.08	0.78
2nd Series	37.8	10	5.94	15.7					
<u>Type 2 (11BR)</u>									
1st Series	48.3	10	7.45	15.4	15*	0.73	4.1	1.69	1.23
2nd Series	34.6	10	8.78	25.3					

*First series only

Fig 8 The strength efficiency, ρ for an infinite bundle vs. the coefficient of variation, C , in the strength of the component filaments.

Fig 9 - Tensile strength versus composition in hybrids of consistent, elastic components

Fig 10 - Observations and bounds for the HMS-HTS system

Fig 11 - Strength predictions (KSI) for glass-HTS carbon

Fig 10 that these simple arguments do not apply to the observations made. At point T the loads carried by both sets of fibres are equal, but when the two fibre breaking strain distributions overlap each other, they are partially additive and this strength trough can be bridged at some level below rule of mixtures. Since the strength recorded at equal proportions of HMS and HTS actually exceeds the rule of mixtures, it is the characteristic reinforcing strength of the HMS fibre that has changed and this must first be explained. The composition range for this transition (which appears to be about 0.45-0.55) is discussed in the Appendix. Then, assuming that the HMS bundle strength is fully realised, it is still necessary to invoke the overlapping strain distributions to explain the strengths observed in the two sets of tests for one part of HMS in three of HTS.

3.2 Overlapping Distributions of Fibre Strain to Break (The Average-to-Bundle Transition)

For this case, where the strength distribution of each set of fibres is already fully effective in a composite, ie the reinforcing strength of each already attains the bundle value, we propose the following approximate treatment. The mean and variance of a normal distribution can be anticipated from those of two contributing distributions (5) as follows.

The weighted mean of breaking strain

$$X = p x_A + q x_B \quad \dots 1$$

with x_A and x_B the means for the components A and B, where the weighting factors $p + q = 1$, and represent the stiffnesses and proportions of A and B respectively. The variance of breaking strain is then

$$V = p^2 V_A + q^2 V_B + V_C \quad \dots 2$$

with V_A , V_B the variances of the component distribution of A and B and V_C is the covariance term, which we suggest be based on

$$2 V_C = p (X - x_A)^2 + q (X - x_B)^2$$

since it must reflect the importance of the spacing between x_A and x_B (there being in effect p readings at x_A , q readings at x_B). We then interpolate Coleman's relationship (Fig 8) to predict the combined bundle strength from the mean fibre strength ($X E_C$) and from the coefficient of variation (C) of combined fibre strength, where $C^2 X^2 = V$ and E_C is the stiffness of the hybrid.

These expressions appear sufficiently general to be applied to multi-component systems, given that it is established first whether or not the strains do overlap. To evaluate the effect of composition on hybrid strength, p and q must be normalised, ie

p is proportional to a E_A

q is proportional to $(1 - a) E_B$

but $p + q = 1$

$$\text{Hence } p = \frac{a E_A}{a E_A + (1 - a) E_B} = a \frac{E_A}{E_C} \text{ and } q = (1 - a) \frac{E_B}{E_C}$$

Substituting for p and q in Eqn 1 shows that $X E_C = a S_A + (1 - a) S_B$, ie the hybrid bundle strength estimate is derived from the proportional average of mean fibre strength, but with a larger variability term, which contains both the individual variances of breaking strain and the spread of the mean strains. This type of calculation has also been applied to make projections for the glass-HTS carbon system (Fig 11) and again shows the bridging of the hybrid strength trough. It also suggests there is little practical advantage here from intimate mixing, which only achieves a minor improvement in strength over a narrow composition range.

Applying this bundle strength calculation to the fibre data of the HMS-HTS system produces a slight dip in strength, eventually following a constant breaking strain line for the HMS of 0.78%. The upper bound used for extrapolating the brittle behaviour of HMS is an assumption of constant defect size taking account of greater work of fracture and lower modulus in the hybrid compositions. This "brittle" line in Fig 10 appears to be an over-estimate of strength, possibly because the observed work of fracture (which includes fibre pull-out) is not entirely effective until a crack has already propagated.

4 Conclusions

1 Fears about the strength of discontinuous fibre composites are largely unwarranted. Unidirectional laminates of HTS fibres cut to lengths some fifteen times their critical length exhibit tensile strengths within ten per cent of those of continuous fibre laminates made from the same fibre batch. Both types of laminate show a high utilisation of fibre strength.

2 Aligned discontinuous fibres in the form of a prepreg sheet are therefore being used with some confidence to prepare components of complex double curvature in which control of alignment must be retained. Used as single plies these sheets can be stretched in the classical composite deformation modes, ie axial, shear and transverse, and can be made economically in finer gauges than can woven fabrics. By pre-plying, the rotational (fabric) mode of deformation can also be introduced. This is a particular advantage at the low ply angles which are inaccessible to a woven material. Use of numerical flow limits and planned rotation of fibres is emphasised to make fabrication simple and reliable. A more detailed understanding of the microscopic flow behaviour and stability is desirable to extend the flow limits of this class of material.

3 Two important mechanisms are found to occur in intimately-mixed unidirectional hybrids. Fibres of nominally brittle behaviour can be isolated sufficiently in a randomly mixed composite that they attain their full reinforcing efficiency - the reinforcing strength of HMS carbon fibre was doubled in this way. Sets of fibres which have overlapping distributions of strain to break also combine to give a hybrid composite which is stronger than the single component values would predict.

4 It appears that if the fibre types are of equal diameter, brittle behaviour can be suppressed completely when the brittle fibre is slightly in the minority. The co-ordination argument which is put forward in the Appendix also suggests that if the brittle fibres have the larger diameter, they need only be in a numerical minority. The conscious overlapping of distributions of fibre breaking strain can in principle be tailored to

maximise energy absorbed on a rising load curve and to minimise the deterioration of hybrid strength below the rule of mixtures value. (It is never less than half.) This procedure will be most effective for improving simple composites which are weak largely because their fibres are highly variable in strength. Certain pitch carbon fibres and asbestos fibres are of this type.

Both the co-ordination and the bundle strength arguments put forward represent upper bounds in that they ignore any local stress-raising effects in one set of fibres caused by the fracture of members of the other set.

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Fig 12 - Fibre-to-fibre model of crack propagation (see appendix)

Appendix

The Brittle - Bundle Transition

In an intimately-mixed hybrid, the fracture of a single fibre is unlikely to be the cause of premature tensile failure. Unless the fibres are very large in diameter, surface damage in preparing test specimens will be several diameters deep, yet the fibre strength is still developed in the composite. In the case of carbon-epoxy composites, we have however shown (6) that notches about 0.25 mm deep had a measurable effect on the strength of composites of heavily surface-treated (HTS) fibres. Zweben (7) presents a theory which considers the stress concentration arising from a fibre fracture in an alternating, two-dimensional hybrid. Here the fracture of a single brittle member cannot be communicated directly to a neighbouring one. This seems appropriate for ordered microstructures containing fibres or bundles of large diameter, including hybrid fabrics and layered hybrids. Our observations on the finely-mixed HMS-HTS system suggest, however, that fracture of isolated HMS fibres has little effect on the HTS fibres but in a randomly mixed, three-dimensional hybrid the existence of a fracture path from one stiff HMS fibre to another is the more dominant factor. This is a topological problem of predicting the effect of composition on available fracture paths.

An attempt is first made to explore the environment surrounding HMS (B) fibres assuming a co-ordination number of five, which is most characteristic of normal, imperfect fibre packing. HTS fibres are assumed to exhibit tough A-type behaviour.

For a CN of five, there are six possible ways of surrounding a fibre, ie 5As, 4A + 1B, 3A + 2B, 2A + 3B, A + 4B, and 5B. If A and B are in the relative proportion $a, b = 1 - a$, then the probability of selecting 5A's is a^5 , similarly that of selecting 5B's is b^5 , and the probabilities for the other conditions are available (8) from the expansion of the binomial $(a + b)^5$. The probability coefficients for these symmetrical expressions are given in Table 5, and the characteristics they represent are:

5A's	an isolated B
4A + 1B	the end member of a B Chain
3A + 2B	part of a single chain or Bs
2A + 3B	part of a double chain, a junction of Bs
A + 4B)	part of a large block of Bs
5B)	

Thus for values of $a = 0.9, b = 0.1$, the B fibres are largely isolated, and the A fibres a virtually continuous block, but in the range 0.4 to 0.6 the mixture consists largely of single and double interwoven chains. Under these conditions one can visualise that consecutive cracking of B fibres could proceed along chains, but that similarly, a single devious chain of A fibres might eventually run right through the thickness of a sample and be used to frustrate crack propagation by providing a weak boundary which can fail in shear. We also note that when $b > .8$, the number of chain end members is very small, suggesting a continuous extensive structure of B.

The next object is, with the least assumptions and preferably with the least calculation, to bracket the estimated composition range in which crack propagation through the B phase ceases to be inhibited by the A. Excluding all other factors local variations in composition will of course prevent the existence of a precise transition. However, we first assume that the average proportions of A and B are maintained in the volumes to be considered, and

attempt a calculation for thin sections, eg shells, laminations and indeed the strip test specimens used in this work. This is shown in Figure 12 which illustrates propagation from a through-thickness edge notch or pre-existing path of B's.

Table 5. The Weighting Effect of Relative Proportions of A and B on Possible Ways of Surrounding a Single B Fibre with Five Other Fibres

Composition		C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆
a	b	(5A)	(4A + B)	(3A + 2B)	(2A + 3B)	(A + 4B)	(5B)
1.0	0	1.0	-	-	-	-	-
0.9	0.1	0.59	0.33	0.07	0.01	-	-
0.8	0.2	0.33	0.41	0.20	0.05	0.006	-
0.7	0.3	0.17	0.36	0.31	0.13	0.03	-
0.6	0.4	0.08	0.26	0.35	0.23	0.07	0.01
0.5	0.5	0.03	0.156	0.31	0.31	0.156	0.03
0.4	0.6	0.01	0.07	0.23	0.35	0.26	0.08
0.3	0.7	-	0.03	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.17
0.2	0.8	-	0.006	0.05	0.20	0.41	0.33
0.1	0.9	-	-	0.01	0.07	0.33	0.59
0	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	1.0

Propagation of cracking through the B phase is presumed to take place where consecutive B fibres exist, but to be frustrated by the presence of a line or path of A fibres. Thus for continuous cracking, the proportion of A (a_s) needed to create a single blocking line must be greater than that of A which actually exists when propagation through B is occurring,

ie if b' is the critical proportion of B at which brittle cracking can first occur, then a_s > (1 - b'). Now the composition for a single line of A's must be numerically the same as that for a single line of B's, ie a_s = b_s

so
$$b_s > (1 - b') \quad \dots\dots 3$$

but b_s < b', since the existence of occasional single lines of B is insufficient to sustain crack propagation, hence

$$b' > (1 - b') \text{ and therefore } b' > 0.5.$$

The total number of fresh lines or paths available during crack propagation from a single line of B's can be estimated directly. Each B consecutively cracked has continuous paths through it, ie for every B surrounded by four other B's, three new paths are introduced, in a rapidly expanding number of routes. Considering a crack passing through an additional population m of mixed fibres, then at the critical composition b', using the notation of Table 5, the total number of paths involved is no greater than

$$1 \times 2^{C'_4 b'm} \times 3^{C'_5 b'm} \times 4^{C'_6 b'm} = Q' \text{ say, or}$$

$$\log Q' = b'm (C'_4 \log 2 + C'_5 \log 3 + C'_6 \log 4) \quad \dots\dots 4$$

(This is an over-estimate of the number of paths, since some must rejoin.)

Now the ease with which such continuity of B occurs, either in single paths or in multiple paths, is governed by the proportion of chain-forming fibres available, and the number of members required in each chain, as well as the size of the original population from which they are chosen. The proportion of chain-making B's available is $b(1 - C_1 - C_2)$ and the probability of selecting r fibres consecutively, to form a chain is therefore $b^r(1 - C_1 - C_2)^r$. Thus the number of chains length r is

$$Q_r \propto b^r (1 - C_1 - C_2)^r \text{ in a given population} \quad \dots 5$$

In the case of single paths of A or B through the thickness of a laminate, r has a characteristic value larger than, but related to, the thickness expressed in fibre diameters, ie $r \sim 10^3$ (which also allows the inclusion of at least one very weak fibre from the strength distribution).

Applying the two expressions (4 and 5) to the special case where, during the initial stage of propagation from a path of r fibres, Q' is changing quickly, but r is virtually constant, gives

$$\left[\frac{Q'}{1} \right]^{\frac{1}{r}} \geq \frac{b' (1 - C'_1 - C'_2)}{b_s (1 - C_1 - C_2)} \quad \dots 6$$

also provided

$$b_s > (1 - b').$$

We take $Q = 1$ for the case of a single path, for although a single path has many related spurs, these will not in general be of sufficient length (r) to qualify, and this is the distinction used here between isolated paths and continuous paths supporting crack propagation. These two inequalities (6 and 3) can be used to generate acceptable values of b_s , b' from different values of the ratio $\frac{m}{r}$. That is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{m}{r} b' (C'_4 \log 2 + C'_5 \log 3 + C'_6 \log 4) \\ & \geq \log [b' (1 - C'_1 - C'_2)] - \log [b_s (1 - C_1 - C_2)] \end{aligned}$$

and $b_s > (1 - b')$, interpolating the coefficients in Table 2 as necessary.

Now the difference between b_s and b' becomes small as m diminishes, ie

$$\frac{m}{r} \geq 2 \quad b' = 0.60, b_s = 0.40$$

$$\frac{m}{r} \geq 1 \quad b' = 0.56, b_s = 0.44$$

$$\frac{m}{r} \geq 0.1 \quad b' = 0.503, b_s = 0.497$$

$$\frac{m}{r} \geq 2.6 \quad b' = 0.7, b_s = 0.3$$

The accuracy with which a transition can be predicted by this means therefore depends on the incremental value of m assumed. There appears to be no reason why it should not be of the same order as r .

It is perfectly possible that a deeper investigation of the theoretical model would determine a narrower transition range than this, but such precision is unlikely to occur in real compositions.